

ISic0514

I.Sicily inscription 0514

Language

Latin

Type

honorific

Material

stone

Object

base

(?)

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

2015.11.12 Metcalfe

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Lilybaeum

Place of origin (modern)

Marsala

Provenance**Coordinates**

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Marsala, Museo Civico di
Marsala

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Cureti vivas
2. pro meritis eximiae lenitatis
3. et benignae administrationis
4. [s]trenuo ac praedicabili iudici
5. Domitio · Zenofilo
6. v(iro) c(larissimo) [corr(ectori)] prov(inciae) Sicil(iae)

Apparatus

Text of CIL

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 491739

EDCS 22000820

Bibliography

Mommsen, Th. 1883. Inscriptiones Bruttiorum Lucaniae Campaniae Siciliae Sardiniae Latinae. Pars posterior. Inscriptiones Siciliae et Sardiniae. *Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum, consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae editum*. Berlin. At 10.7234 (<http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/item/buchseite/650778>)

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